

THYMUS VULGARIS FROM MEDEA ALGERIA AS AN ENHANCEMENT OF ZINGIBER OFFICINALE ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY FOR A BETTER EFFICIENCY IN COMPARISON TO ANTIBIOTICS

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Abstract

This study aims at determining and evaluating the antimicrobial activity of *Zingiber officinale* and *Thymus vulgaris* extracts and their combination. The antimicrobial effect of ginger, thyme and their associations were evaluated *in vitro* against 25 microbial strains using the disc diffusion and agar dilution methods. The results indicated that ginger and thyme extracts showed antimicrobial activity against all microorganisms tested. The highest activity was against *Staphylococcus sp* and *Listeria monocytogenes* ATCC 15313 with significant inhibition zones greater than 35 mm (P-value = 0.0057) when thyme ethanolic extract was used. The minimum inhibitory concentration MIC of *T. Vulgaris* ethanolic extract against *B. subtilis* ATCC6631 was the lowest 0.145 mg/ml followed by the MIC of ginger ethanolic extract 100 mg/ml. The MIC of the combined extract was 122.5 mg/ml against all strains. The effect of the combined extract of thyme and ginger TEGE shows high sensitivity (40mm) compared to those of antibiotics (\approx 25mm) towards *E.coli* ATCC11150. As for the antimycobacterial effect, our results showed that the thyme ethanolic extract had an efficient antimycobacterial effect. The pharmacologically active molecules of *Thymus Vulgaris* and ginger were identified by GC-MS.

Keywords: Antimicrobial; Antimycobacterial; Thymus Vulgaris; Zingiber officinale; Combination extracts.GC-MS.

INTRODUCTION

Microbial resistance to antimicrobial agents is emerging as a major public health concern today. Pathogenic bacteria are the cause of various food diseases and poisoning. The emergence and dissemination of resistant bacterial strains result from the uncontrolled and excessive use of antibiotics [1]. Although first-line antibiotics are sufficient to treat most patients infected with strains of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, the rate of treatment efficacy has been declining in recent years due to the emergence of strains resistant to conventional treatments, those called multi-resistant strains [2]. Unfortunately, many other microorganisms have developed resistance to the various antibiotics used in the treatment of serious infections. This has forced researchers to explore new antimicrobial substances from various sources such as new inhibitory agents. Recent reports have described the role of herbal remedies in preventing and treating many infections [3].

The use of medicinal plants to prevent or cure disease was one of the earliest therapeutic practices in human history [4]. Many plants such as ginger and thyme have been used to treat infectious diseases, as they possess antimicrobial properties against pathogenic fungi and bacteria [5, 6]. In addition, the secondary metabolites of these plants are known as inhibitory agents without side effects [7]. The main components of *Z. officinale*, 6-shogaol and 6-Gingerol have shown an antiproliferative effect on several tumor cell lines. Ginger extract has potent anti-cancer activity against pancreatic cancer cells. In fact, the ethanolic extract of ginger suppressed the progression of the cell cycle; therefore, it caused the death of pancreatic cancer cells [8, 9].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The chemicals, Paper Discs (Antibiotic Assay), growth mediums, and Paper Discs for absorbency (Antimicrobial Substances) were kindly delivered by Saidal Antibiotical Laboratories (Saidal Industries, Medea 26000, Algeria). The plant material used in this study was obtained from the local market of Médéa, Algeria. Rhizomes of fresh ginger from China species "*Zingiber officinale*", and thyme leaves species "*Thymus Vulgaris*" original from Medea (Algeria). The aerial parts of *Thymus Vulgaris* were collected between July and September from Medea (Algeria), namely Ouamri Municipality, thyme species were identified by botanists working at Medea Yahia Fares University. Four solvent systems were chosen separately, acetone (96%) and ethanol (96%) alone, and these same solvents in 70% and 30% of the distilled water in order to vary the polarity of the solvents. The extraction was carried out by macerating 50g of plant in 500ml of solvent for 24 hours in a closed container and at room temperature. After 24 hours, the solution is filtered through a 150mm diameter filter, then the solvent is separated from the extract using a device called a Rotavapor "rotary evaporator". To test the antimicrobial effect of the association/ combination between *Zingiberofficinale* and *thymus Vulgaris*, emulsions were prepared which are mixtures of the ethanolic and acetone extracts already prepared by using Twin 80 as emulsifiant (emulsifiers). The choice of these extracts depends on their compared effectiveness.

Microbial Materials

In this study, 25 microbial strains were used:

18 referenced strains (American Type Culture Collection ATCC) were kindly supplied by Saidal Antibiotic Laboratories (Saidal Industries, Algeria). As well as 7 isolate strains which are:

- 5 bacterial strains were isolated from human samples and identified at the Bacteriology Laboratory of a Local Public Health Establishment Medea (Algeria): *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus mirabilis*, and *Bacillus subtilis*.
- 2 mycobacterium strains were isolated from human sputum, and identified at the Tuberculosis and Respiratory Disease Control Service Zoubayria-Medea (Algeria): Human *Mycobacterium Tuberculosis*.

All these microorganisms are pathogenic with different potentials depending on the type of infections caused and are responsible for nosocomial infections and resistant to antibiotics, which motivated their choice.

Table 1: Microbial strains and their growth mediums

num	Microorganisms	Code	Gram	growth mediums	incubation temperatures
1	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 43300	St	+	Chapman Agar	37 °C
2	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 25923	Sb	+	Chapman	37 °C
3	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 29213	SA2	+	Chapman	37 °C
4	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> isolated	SA3	+	Chapman	37 °C
5	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 6538	SAf	+	Chapman	37 °C
6	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i> ATCC 12228	SE	+	Chapman	37 °C
7	<i>Listeria monocytogene</i> ATCC 15313	Lis	+	Nutrient Agar	37 °C
8	<i>Entérocoques feacalis</i> ATCC 29212	ECBC	+	Nutrient Agar	37 °C
9	<i>Entérocoques feacalis</i> ATCC 6569	EsF	+	Nutrient Agar	37 °C
10	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> isolated	B1	+	Nutrient Agar	37 °C
11	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> ATCC23857	B2	+	Nutrient Agar	37 °C
12	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> ATCC6631	B3	+	Nutrient Agar	37 °C
13	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i> ATCC23350	B4	+	Nutrient Agar	37 °C
14	<i>proteus mirabilis</i> isolated	u	-	Hektoen	37 °C
15	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> ATCC9027	Pseudo F	-	MacConkey	37 °C
16	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> isolated	Pseudo	-	MacConkey	37 °C
17	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC 25922	E1	-	Hektoen	37 °C
18	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC 25622	E2	-	Hektoen	37 °C
19	<i>Escherichia coli</i> isolated	E3	-	Hektoen	37 °C
20	<i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC11150	E4	-	Hektoen	37 °C
21	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> ATCC 4352	klb	-	Hektoen	37 °C
22	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> ATCC19763	SS		Sabouraud Agar	25 °C
23	<i>Candida albicans</i> ATCC10231	Ca		Sabouraud Agar	25 °C

Preparation of inoculum

The revivification of the different bacterial species is carried out by successive passage through nutrient agar. Each species was seeded beforehand on nutrient agar, to obtain a culture of 18 to 24 hours. Then, 5 well isolated bacterial colonies are suspended in physiological water at 0.9% NaCl. This suspension is then adjusted to the McFarland 0.5 standard using a Spectrophotometer (Apparatus: VWR UV-1600 PC Spectrophotometer), corresponding to an optical density OD between 0.08 to 0.1 read at 625 nm, which corresponds to a suspension containing approximately 108 bacteria/ml and 104 yeasts/ml [10].

Antimicrobial activity

The antimicrobial activity was carried out using the disc diffusion method on the agar medium of Muller Hinton (MH) for bacterial strains and Sabouraud (SB) for fungal strains. This method has been standardized by the National Standards Committee for Clinical Laboratories (NCCLS) [11].

Paper Discs, 9 mm in diameter, were separately impregnated with 30 μg = 15 μl of each tested extract (extracts prepared from ginger, thyme and their associations) deposited on the surface of the inoculated Petri dish. A prepared antibiotic control disc was applied to the same dishes, Amoxicillin, Gentamicin and Cefazolin 30 μg for the bacterial strains, and for the fungal strains Fluconazole, these discs served as an effective positive control against the microbial species [10].

Moreover, 200 μl (0.2ml) of each extract was poured on the surface of Lowenstein-Jensen medium inoculated by human isolated *mycobacterium Tuberculosis* in order to determine the antimycobacterial activity of these plants (Fig. 13).

Incubation and reading

After 24 hours of incubation at 37 °C for bacteria and 48 hours of incubation at 25 °C for yeasts. The antimicrobial activity was assessed by measuring the inhibition diameter of the growth zone in millimeters formed around the disc (including the diameter of the disc which is 9 mm). The manipulations are repeated 3 times for each test. The rating scale for antimicrobial activity given by Mutai et al. (2009) was followed. The latter classified the substance tested according to the diameter of the zone of inhibition (D) of microbial growth into five classes: Non-inhibiting: $D < 10$ mm, slightly inhibitory: $11\text{mm} \leq D \leq 16$ mm, moderately inhibitory: $16\text{ mm} \leq D \leq 20$ mm, strongly inhibitory: $21\text{ mm} \leq D \leq 29$ mm, Very strongly inhibitory: $D \geq 30$ mm [12].

Statistical analysis

The test results are expressed as mean \pm SD. The difference between the control and the different tests is determined by univariate analysis of variance (ANOVA) for comparison of means and determination of significance rates. Values of $p \leq 0.05$ are considered statistically significant. The boxplot is an efficient method of graphically presenting numeric data that has been calculated using python 3.6. Python is an analysis program for plotting and visualizing data as graphs [13-14]. Programming Python (Vol. 8). O'Reilly Company).

Graphic presentation by boxplot

Boxplots are used to visualize and compare the distribution and central tendency of numerical values via their quartiles. Quartiles are used to split numeric values into four equal groups based on five key values: minimum, first quartile, median, third quartile, and maximum (Figure.1.a).

Figure 1: a) Graphical representation of boxplot. b) Different variables and their percentages

Graphic information

We can get an idea of the central tendency of the inhibition zones of each extract by observing the position of the median (M). The median makes it possible to determine 50% of the zones of inhibitions measured. That is to say, if M is between 10-20 mm with a value of 17 mm; therefore, 50% of the strains have a zone of inhibitions of 17 mm. The value of the 1st quartile Q1 (25% of the zones), corresponding to the lower line of the box, allows us to determine 25% of the weakest zones. The value of the 3rd quartile Q3 (75% of the zones), corresponding to the upper line of the box, makes it possible to determine 25% of the zones which have values greater than the median (Figure 1. b). The 2 lower and upper "whiskers", represented here by the small vertical rectangles on either side of the box. These 2 whiskers, present the minimum and maximum inhibitory zones of each extract. For example, if the maximum value equals 36 mm, the greatest zone of inhibition of the extract is 36 mm. These variables allow us to determine the best extract with high efficiency on the 23 strains studied.

Gas chromatography – mass spectrometry (GC-MS)

GC-MS is a quality control pointed to determine the most pharmacologically active compounds of *Thymus Vulgaris* and *Zingiber officinale*. The analysis was carried out at the Laboratory of the Scientific Police of Algiers. Apparatus: GC MS model CLARUS 500 brand Perkin-Elmer.

GC- MS method

The experimental conditions of the GC-MS system were as follows: standard non-polar column TR 5-MS capillary, dimension: 30 Mts, ID: 0.25 mm, film thickness: 0.25 μm . Flow of the mobile phase (carrier gas: He) was adjusted to 1 ml min⁻¹. In the gas chromatography part, temperature program (oven temperature) was raised from 40 °C to 220 °C at 4 °C min⁻¹ and the injection volume was 1 μl . Samples were run fully at a range of 20 and 550 m/z and the results were compared using the Wiley and Nist Spectral Library search Programme. [15-16]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effect of ginger on Gram + and Gram - bacteria

It is noted that the ethanolic and pure acetone extracts show an interesting antibacterial activity against gram-positive bacteria (figure 2). By citing *S. aureus* ATCC 43300 and *S. aureus* ATCC6538 with inhibition zones diameters reached 26.00 mm, 28.00 mm by the ethanolic extract (GE) and 20.00 mm, 24.67 mm with acetone extract (GA) respectively. Other positive responses were recorded with three other bacterial strains: *Listeria monocytogene* ATCC 15313, *Enterococci faecalis* ATCC 29212, and *S. epidermidis* ATCC 12228. However, these extracts show only weak activity against *Bacillus sp.* Figure 3 and Figure 4 summarizes the results of ginger extracts inhibition zones diameters on gram-negative bacteria. Indeed, gram-negative bacteria, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 9027, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* ATCC 9027, *E. coli* ATCCC 25922 and *E. coli* ATCC 25622 were found to be resistant to all extracts (≤ 10 mm). The other strains show certain sensitivity to the two extracts (GE and GA). The best inhibition zones diameters are between 11 and 14 mm with *Escherichia coli* ATCC 4352, and *Proteus mirabilis* isolated. On the other hand, these extracts showed low activity against *Saccaromycescervisiae* ATCC 19763 (10 and 09.5 mm), and *Candida albicans* ATCC 10231 (10 and 09.5 mm). And the acetone extract at 70 % showed no effect against these strains. Figure 5 illustrates these results. The results show that only pure ethanolic and acetone ginger extracts with no change in polarity have antimicrobial activity against bacteria and fungi, particularly, ethanolic ginger extract (GE) which has significant inhibitory activity. This is confirmed by other studies which indicate that ethanolic ginger extract inhibits the growth of certain Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria, as well as respiratory pathogens *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Haemophilus influenzae* [17, 18]. Our results are similar to those obtained by the work carried out by Amari S. [19], which indicates that two ginger extracts tested exhibit varying levels of activity depending on the following bacteria: *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Micrococcus luteus*, and *Staphylococcus aureus* which appeared to be sensitive to the action of the two extracts with inhibition diameters between 13 and 27 mm. The results obtained from recent work by Fadli Mariam and Abd-Alrahman et al. [20-21] and Riaz et al. [22] state that the methanolic and chloroformic extracts of ginger are active in vitro against the same range of bacteria. In addition, they have found that 10-geringol and 12-gingerol from the ginger rhizome have shown antibacterial activity in vitro against a broad spectrum of bacteria, particularly anaerobic

bacteria associated with periodontitis of the human oral cavity [17, 22]. We noticed the absence of gingerols in our ginger ethanolic extract that contains 8 active molecules (see Fig 15 and Table 8).

Fig. 2. Effect of ginger on gram + bacteria, Standard deviation: black bar. ST: *S.aureus* ATCC 43300 – SB : *S.aureus* ATCC 25923 – S2: *S.aureus* 29213 – S3: *S.aureus* isolated – SF3: *S.aureus* ATCC 6538– SE: *S.epidermidis* ATCC 12228– LIS: *L.monocytogene* ATCC 15313– ECBE : *E.feacalis* ATCC 29212– ESF: *E.feacalis* ATCC 6569–B1: *B.subtilis* isolated– B2:*B.subtilis* ATCC23857- B3: *B.subtilis* ATCC6631– B4:*B.amyloliquefaciens* ATCC23350

Fig. 3: Effect of ginger on gram- bacteria, Standard deviation: black bar. U: *P.mirabilis* isolated –Pseudo f : *p.aerogenosae* ATCC 9027– Pseudo : *p.aerogenosae* isolated – E1 : *E.coli* ATCC25922 – E2 : *E.coli* ATCC25622 –E3: *E.coli* isolated – E4F: *E.coli* ATCC4352– KLB: *K.pneumoniae* ATCC 9027.

Fig. 4: Effect of ginger on fungal strains, Saccaro: *S.cervisiae* ATCC 19763 – Candida: *C.albicans* ATCC 10231

Fig. 5: Effect of *thymus vulgaris* on gram + bacteria, Standard deviation: black bar. ST : *S.aureus* ATCC 43300 – SB : *S.aureus* ATCC 25923 – S2: *S.aureus* 29213 – S3: *S.aureus* isolated – SF3 : *S.aureus* ATCC 6538– SE : *S.epidermidis* ATCC 12228– LIS : *L.monocytogene* ATCC 15313– ECBE : *E.feacalis* ATCC 29212– ESF: *E.feacalis* ATCC 6569 –B1 : *B.subtilis* ATCC23857– B2 : *B.subtilis* isolated – B3 : *B.subtilis* ATCC6631– B4 : *B.amyloliquefaciens* ATCC23350

Evaluation of the antimicrobial activity of *thymus vulgaris*

From our results, we noticed that almost all extracts from thyme are endowed with a strong antibacterial power, even by changing the polarity of solvents. The antimicrobial activity of different thyme extracts is evaluated on 13 bacterial strains (Figure 5). In fact, 5 strains of *S. aureus* and a strain of *S. epedermidus* ATCC12228, give a high

sensitization to both ethanolic and acetone extracts with inhibitions zones ranging between 26.33 and 40 mm. Likewise, *L. monocytogen* ATCC15313 shows a high sensitivity to extracts with inhibitions zones greater than 30 mm. The antimicrobial effect of thyme extracts on gram-negative bacteria is shown in figure 6. On the other hand, Gram-negative showed more resistance to these extracts than Gram-positive, but it should be noted that these strains are sensitive due to their diameter of inhibition which is greater than 10 mm. While the weakest antimicrobial activity is given by *P. aerogenos* isolated which does not show any sensitivity towards all the extracts of thymus *Vulgaris*. Also that *E. coli* ATCC 25622 was inhibited only by the acetone extract with a zone of ≈ 10 mm. The other gram-negative bacteria (*P. mirabilis* isolated, *P. aerogenosa* ATCC 9027 and *E. coli* ATCC 25922, *E. coli* isolated, *E. coli* ATCC11150 and *K. pneumoniae* ATCC 9027) show intermediate resistance to these extracts which does not exceed 16mm (Figure 6). In addition, fungal strains were inhibited by *thymus Vulgaris* extracts. The best activity was due to the ethanolic extract (ET) which inhibited the two strains with diameters greater than 20 mm (see figure 7). The mode of action of thyme extracts depends primarily on their compositions and the hydrophobic property of their constituents, as well as their high levels of phenols such as carvacrol and thymol (see Fig 14 and Table 7) which are phenolic compounds known for their antimicrobial properties [21]. And Zohary M et al [23] and according to dorman et al. [24] thymol is the compound with the broadest spectrum of antibacterial activity, followed by carvacrol and α -terpineol [25-28].

Fig. 6: Effect of thyme on gram- bacteria, Standard deviation: black bar. U: *P.mirabilis* isolated–Pseudo f : *p.aerogenosae* ATCC 9027– Pseudo : *p.aerogenosae* isolated – E1 : *E.coli* ATCC25922 – E2 : *E.coli* ATCC25622 –E3: *E.coli* isolé – E4F: *E.coli* ATCC4352–KLB: *K.pneumoniae* ATCC 9027

Fig. 7: Effect of thyme on fungal strains Saccaro: *S.cervisiae* ATCC 19763 – Candida: *C.albicans* ATCC 10231

Boxplot of extracts action against 23 strains

In this regard, the following figures (a) and (b) present a comparison of the antimicrobial activity of all extracts against the 23 strains tested in order to find out which extract is more effective (Figure 8).

The median of the ethanolic ginger extract (GE) is 13.00 mm with the value of Q1 is 10.73mm and Q3 is 26.00mm and a maximum value is 35.67 mm, which indicates that the ethanolic extract of ginger (GE) is the best compared to other GEE, GA and GAE ginger extracts.

As a result, it is considered to be the most effective ginger extract with the greatest inhibition zones against all tested strains. According to the analysis of variance (ANOVA) which determines, the P-value of ginger is 0.0040 which is considered statistically significant (Figure 8 (a)).

Similarly, figure 8 (b) presents a comparison between thyme extracts (P-value = 0.0057). The results show that the ethanolic thymus extract (TE) is the most effective with a median of 21.00 mm, with Q1 of 11mm and its Q3 equal to 36.33mm and a maximum value is 40.00mm, followed by the acetone extract TA which has a median of 15.33mm and with quartile values of Q1 (11.75mm) and Q3 (26.33mm) and a value maximum of 36mm.

Fig. 8: The average effect of different extracts from thymus and ginger

Evaluation of the antimicrobial activity of the associations

In this section, the pure ethanolic and acetone extracts of ginger and thyme were used to prepare four different combination extracts which are shown in Table 2. According to (figures 9, 10 and 11) and table 3, it can be seen that the extracts antimicrobial effect becomes greater when they are mixed. The results obtained show that the effect of both ethanolic and acetone extracts of ginger increases when they are combined with thyme extracts; therefore, there will be a potentiation effect for these extracts.

In fact, the highest inhibitory values are obtained by the TEGE and TEGA extracts for all the strains tested. The association results presented in figure 9 indicate that in almost all strains of *Staphylococcus* and *L. monocytogenes* ATCC 15313, the inhibitory zones of the TEGE extract are the largest with a diameter of 40mm, followed by the TEGA extract values with inhibition zones between 25-40mm. On the other hand, the *bacillus* sp presents an intermediate sensitivity to the extracts tested.

In addition, gram-bacteria showed resistance to these extracts (see figure 10), except *E. coli* ATCC4352 which showed high sensitivity with inhibition zones exceeding 25mm. Moreover, *P. aerogenosa* isolated does not show any sensitivity towards all the extracts of thyme and ginger separately previously tested, but this strain becomes sensitive to GETE with a zone of 25mm.

One can say that we had a potentiation of the effect of the extracts after their combination. In addition, in figure 11, the inhibitory effect of the combined extracts on the fungal strains was characterized by zones of inhibition greater than 18mm.

Fig. 9: Effect of the combination of extracts on gram + bacteria. ST :*S.aureus* ATCC 43300 – SB : *S.aureus* ATCC 25923 – S2: *S.aureus* 29213 – S3: *S.aureus* isolated – SF3 : *S.aureus* ATCC 6538–SE : *S.epidermidis* ATCC 12228– LIS : *L.monocytogenes* ATCC 153 15313– ECBE : *E.feacalis* ATCC 29212– ESF: *E.feacalis* ATCC 6569 –B1 : *B.subtilis* isolated – B2 :*B.subtilis* ATCC23857–B3 : *B.subtilis* ATCC6631– B4 : *B.amyloliquefaciens* ATCC23350.

More precisely, *C. Albicans* shows a high sensitivity with the four association/associated extracts with an inhibition zone exceeding 40mm, resulting in an effect potentiation. In figure 12, the medians of the extracts (TAGA) and (TAGE) are between 10 and 15mm followed by the extract (TEGA) with a median of 22 mm, while the median of the ethanolic extract of ginger and thyme (TEGE) is 24.5mm which has a maximum value of 40mm. As well as Q1 exceeds 15mm and Q3 equals 38mm, which indicates that this extract(TEGE) is the best compared to the others (P-value=0.052). Thus, other works have evaluated the essential oil combination effect of *Thymus Vulgaris L* with other essential oils, where they found that the addition of thyme increases the inhibitory effect [28].

Fig. 10: Effect of the combination on gram- bacteria. U: *P.mirabilis* isolated – Pseudo f : *p.aerogenosae* ATCC 9027– Pseudo : *p.aerogenosae* isolated – E1 : *E.coli* ATCC25922 – E2 : *E.coli* ATCC25622 –E3: *E.coli* isolated – E4F: *E.coli* ATCC4352–KLB: *K.pneumoniae* ATCC 9027

Fig. 11: Effect of the extracts combination on fungal strains, Saccaro : *S.cervisiae* ATCC 19763 –Candida : *C.albicans* ATCC 10231

Fig. 12: The average effect of different extracts of the combination of *Z. officinale* and *T. vulgaris*

Table 2: Shows the different association probabilities

Extract	TA	TE
GA	TAGA	TEGA
GE	TAGE	TEGE

Determination of minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC)

Based on antimicrobial activity tested on 23 strains, the obtained results confirmed that ethanolic extracts of *T. Vulgaris*, *Z. officinal* and their combination are the most effective, almost on all the tested strains. Particularly, *S. aureus* ATCC 43300, *S. aureus* ATCC 6538, *L.monocytogenes* ATCC 15313 and *B. subtilis* ATCC6631 showed higher sensitivity. In order to determine the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of these strains, the method of dilution in a liquid medium was used (see Table 4, Table 5, and Table 6).

The results obtained show that the lowest minimum inhibitory concentration of *T. Vulgaris* extract is 0.145 mg/ml (10^{-4} dilution) against *B. subtilis* ATCC6631, followed by a concentration of 1.145 mg/ml (dilution 10^{-3}) towards *L. monocytogenes* ATCC 15313 and *S. aureus* ATCC 6538, as well as the strain *S. aureus* ATCC 43300 does not show any sensitivity.

Unlike the ethanolic extract of *Z.officinale* which showed higher MIC values compared to that of *T. Vulgaris*, the only minimum inhibitory concentration is 100 mg/ml against *B. subtilis* ATCC6631 and *S. aureus* ATCC 6538 , while the two other strains *S. aureus* ATCC 43300 and *L. monocytogene* ATCC 15313 are more resistant and showed no MIC. To determine the minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) of the combined extracts

(TEGE), all the strains tested showed sensitivity with a MIC=122.5 mg/ml (10^{-1} dilution). The MIC value of ethanolic ginger extract found in our study is relatively high (100mg/ml) compared to the MIC value of ethanolic and methanolic extract of (0.0064 to 20 mg/ml) against *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis* found by (Bhargava et al. [29]; Abd-Alrahman al. [20]; Nikolić et al. [30]. While Azu N et al. [31] showed no sensitivity towards the ethanolic extract of *Z. officinale* against *Bacillus subtilis*, which does not match our results.

Table 4: The MICs values of *Z.officinale*.

The different dilutions of <i>Z. officinale</i> in mg/ml												
D	10^{-1}	10^{-2}	10^{-3}	10^{-4}	10^{-5}	10^{-6}	10^{-7}	10^{-8}	10^{-9}	10^{-10}	10^{-11}	C
mg/ml	10^2	10^1	1	10^{-1}	10^{-2}	10^{-3}	10^{-4}	10^{-5}	10^{-6}	10^{-7}	10^{-8}	-
St	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
SF	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Lis	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B3	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Table 5: The MICs values of *T.vulgaris*

The different dilutions of <i>T.vulgaris</i> (TE) in mg/ml												
D	10^{-1}	10^{-2}	10^{-3}	10^{-4}	10^{-5}	10^{-6}	10^{-7}	10^{-8}	10^{-9}	10^{-10}	10^{-11}	C
mg/ml	145	14.5	1.45	1.45. 10^{-1}	1.45. 10^{-2}	1.45. 10^{-3}	1.45. 10^{-4}	1.45. 10^{-5}	1.45. 10^{-6}	1.45. 10^{-7}	1.45. 10^{-8}	-
St	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
SF	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Lis	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B3	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Table 6: The MICs values of *T. Vulgaris* and *Z. officinale* Combination

The different dilutions of <i>T. Vulgaris</i> and <i>Z. officinale</i> Combination in mg/ml												
D	10^{-1}	10^{-2}	10^{-3}	10^{-4}	10^{-5}	10^{-6}	10^{-7}	10^{-8}	10^{-9}	10^{-10}	10^{-11}	C
mg/ml	122.5	12.25	1.225	1.225. 10^{-1}	1.225. 10^{-2}	1.225. 10^{-3}	1.225. 10^{-4}	1.225. 10^{-5}	1.225. 10^{-6}	1.225. 10^{-7}	1.225. 10^{-8}	-
St	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
SF	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Lis	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
B3	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

D: dilution; C: Control (Bacteria + liquid medium).

+: presence of bacterial growth

-: absence of bacterial growth.

St: *S.aureus* ATCC 43300.

SF: *S.aureus* ATCC 6538.

Lis: *L.monocytogene* ATCC 15313

B3: *B.subtilis* ATCC6631.

Comparison between the effectiveness of extracts with antibiotics

Staphylococcus aureus showed a variation in sensitivity between the antibiotics and the extracts. *S. aureus* ATCC 29213 showed a dominant sensitivity to the ethanolic extract of thymus Vulgaris with a value of 38.00mm higher than those of the antibiotics used. While, *S. aureus* ATCC 43300 and *S. aureus* ATCC 25923 showed high sensitivity to amoxicillin up to 50mm, followed by similar sensitivity to the ethanolic extract of *T. Vulgaris* TE, and the association TEGE with inhibition zones exceeding 40mm (See Table 3).

The effect of Gentamicin and the ethanolic extract of ginger (GE) are identical on the *S. aureus* ATCC 43300 strain with inhibition zones close to 30mm. It is noteworthy that the effect of the combined extract of thyme and ginger TEGE shows a really high sensitivity (40mm) compared to those of antibiotics (\approx 25mm) towards *E. coli* ATCC11150. Likewise, this extract shows similar activity to Gentamicin towards isolated *P. aerogenosae*. While, *C. Albicans* ATCC 10231 has shown a dominant sensitivity for the TEGE extract with a 38mm inhibition zone as well as resistant to the antifungal (Fluconazole).

Assessment of anti-mycobacterium activity

Strains of *M. tuberculosis* are conventionally identified by the morphology of the colonies on the ridges of Lowenstein-Jensen agar. The appearance of these colonies is rough, beige with irregular cauliflower-shaped edges. The two strains of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* treated with different extracts: ethanolic extract of ginger (GE), ethanolic extract of thyme (TE), and their associations (TEGE) are shown in Figure 13. Figure 13 (c), 13 (d) show no colony proliferation on the surface of tubes of ethanolic thyme extract (tubes 5 in (c) and tube 4 in (d)) which indicates the thyme antimycobacterium effect.

On the one hand, the inhibitory effect of (TEGE) is clearly apparent in tubes 6. On the other hand, the tubes of ethanolic ginger extract (GE) and the untreated controls gave mycobacterial mats (tubes 3 in (c and d) tube 4 in (c) and tube 5 in (d)). According to the results obtained, the ethanolic extract of thyme has an antimycobacterial effect, and this is confirmed by Jimenez-Arellanes et al. [32].

Fig. 13: Assessment of antimycobacteria activity. (a) Inoculation of sample No. 1. (d) Sampling zoom N ° 1. Tube1: patient sample. Tube2: unseeded tube. Tube3: Control. Tube4: TE. Tube5: GE. Tube6: TEGE. (b) Inoculation of sample No. 2. (c) Sampling zoom N ° 2. Tube1: patient sample. Tube2: unseeded tube. Tube3: Control. Tube4: GE. Tube5: TE. Tube6: TEGE.

Analysis of *Thymus Vulgaris* and *Zingiber officinale* extract with GC-MS

Major constituents (7 molecules) of *Thymus Vulgaris* extract identified by GC-MS were presented in Fig 14 and table 7.

The gas chromatography mass spectrum GC-MS, reveals that *Zingiber officinale* extract contains eight different molecules (See Fig 15 and Table 8).

Fig.14: GC-MS spectrum of *Thymus vulgaris* ethanol extract

Fig. 15: GC-MS spectrum of *Zingiber Officinale* ethanol extract

Table 7: The molecules composing the *Thymus Vulgaris* ethanol extract obtained by CG-MS analysis

Molecule	Retention time / min	Molecular weight / g mol ⁻¹
THYMOL	17.57	150
CARVACROL	17.57	150
P-TERT -BUTYL CATECHOL	22.09	166
N-HEXADECANOIC ACID	36.38	256
9, 12-OCT ADECADIENOICACID (Z,Z)	40.47	280
13 -OCT ADECENAL, (Z)	40.76	280
OLEIC ACID	41.04	282

Table 8: The molecules composing the *zingiber officinale* ethanol extract obtained by GC-MS analysis

Molecule name	Retention time / min	Molecular weight g mol ⁻¹
Aromadendrene	27.67	204
β-Curcumene	23.51	202
Zingiberene	23.76	204
Alpha farnesene	24.46	204
β-Sesquiphellandrene	25.01	204
Nerolidol	25.76	222
β-Farnesene	29.59	204
Xanthorrhizol	31.04	218

Tableau 3: Antibacterial effect of different extracts

	GE	GEE	GA	GAE	TE	TEE	TA	TAE	TAGA	TA GE	TEG A	TEG E	AMC	CEF	GEN	FLU
ST	26.00±3.97	9.33±0.47	20.00±4.08	11.67±3.09	40.00±0.00	22.00±1.63	33.00±7.26	20.67±2.49	40	30	40	40	50.33±1.25	41.66±1.69	27±1.9	-
SB	20.00±2.03	10.00±0.82	14.00±4.80	14.33±2.05	37.67±1.70	23.33±1.7	36.00±2.94	25.00±0.00	34	40	30	40	60.00±1.63	46.00±4.90	30±0.0	-
S2	12.33±2.05	10.33±0.47	17.33±2.05	14.67±3.00	38.00±1.63	21.67±2.36	35.67±6.02	21.33±0.94	26	24	32	25	26.66±2.49	33.05±2.16	33.02±1.2	-
S3	29.67±0.47	12.33±2.62	8.00±4.00	0.00±0.00	34.00±1.27	27.67±2.05	37.67±3.3	23.67±2.87	36	23	25	23	42.66±2.05	32.00±2.44	35.01±1.0	-
SAF	28.00±2.45	29.00±3.56	24.67±4.11	21.67±4.5	39.67±0.47	39.33±0.94	29.33±0.94	25.33±3.77	40	40	40	40	43.33±2.49	31.66±1.24	32.00±0.0	-
SE	27.00±2.45	13.67±2.36	23.33±2.49	19.00±4.55	39.67±0.47	39.33±0.94	26.33±0.47	25.00±0.00	40	40	40	40	42.66±1.88	34.00±2.44	33.04±1.0	-
LIS	35.67±3.3	15.33±5.56	29.33±3.4	31.67±6.20	36.33±0.94	35.67±1.7	31.67±2.36	30.67±1.7	40	34	40	40	56.00±4.32	57.66±1.69	36.00±0.0	-
ECBC	18.00±2.04	13.33±4.78	14.67±2.87	09.00±4.50	13.33±2.36	0.00±0.00	26.00±0.82	11.00±0.82	12	11	17	26	37.66±5.55	32.66±1.69	16.03±2.5	-
ESF	15.67±2.62	9.33±0.47	11.00±1.63	9.00±4.50	10.33±1.25	11.00±1.63	14.67±0.47	0.00±0.00	00	00	23	17	40.33±2.05	31.66±2.05	18.00±0.0	-
B1	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	18.33±2.94	10.00±0.82	15.00±0.00	11.00±0.00	12	11	20	24	43.33±2.49	32.14±0.81	35.7±1.5	-
B2	10.67±0.47	10.33±0.94	11.33±1.25	0.00±0.00	11.00±1.41	0.00±0.00	11.67±1.7	16.00±1.41	23	20	28	25	44.66±6.76	30.00±0.00	38.4±2.6	-
B3	11.67±2.36	9.33±0.47	24.33±4.5	22.00±6.5	10.67±0.47	0.00±0.00	21.00±0.82	11.00±0.82	11	15	22	23	24.66±4.98	33.15±5.71	34.00±0.0	-
B4	8.00±3.72	9.00±0.57	18.67±5.7	11.00±2.83	14.00±1.41	10.67±1.7	12.67±0.47	10.00±0.82	12	15	10	17	21.66±1.69	23.33±1.24	22.7±1.2	-
U	11.67±2.36	0.00±0.00	11.00±2.83	8.33±4.5	11.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	13.67±0.47	0.00±0.00	11	11	11	11	13.00±1.41	30.66±2.05	20.8±0.3	-
Pseud f	9.00±0.00	9.00±0.00	13.00±1.63	11.00±0.00	11.33±1.89	10.00±1.41	11.67±2.36	12.00±1.41	12	11	17	15	14.33±0.47	18.20±2.86	28.60±4.2	-
Pseudo	11.00±1.41	0.00±0.00	14.33±2.05	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	11	11	18	25	12.66±2.08	14.00±2.86	21.15±1.6	-
E1	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	11.00±2.42	10.33±0.47	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	00	00	00	00	10.33±0.47	15.33±2.82	28.00±0.0	-
E2	9.33±0.47	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	00.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	10.33±0.47	0.00±0.00	09	09	11	09	34.66±2.24	30.00±2.82	25.5±3.2	-
E3	11.67±2.36	09.33±4.24	8.67±4.78	0.00±0.00	16.67±2.24	10.00±0.82	18.00±2.16	9.00±4.9	13	11	13	11	23.00±0.81	25.66±1.24	22.00±0.0	-
E4f	13.00±1.63	08.33±4.5	13.00±2.97	13.00±2.45	14.00±2.83	11.67±3.09	14.00±2.94	12.00±2.8	30	37	28	36	23.66±2.62	26.33±2.05	22.4±1.9	-
KLB	11.33±2.62	08.00±4.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	9.00±3.24	0.00±0.00	10.33±1.25	0.00±0.00	11	11	11	11	25.33±1.24	28.00±2.16	33.45±0.1	-
Saccaro	14.67±1.25	11.33±0.94	11.00±0.82	0.00±0.00	21.33±1.7	19.67±2.87	23.33±0.94	19.00±0.94	25	25	20	18	-	-	-	22.33±0.5
Candida	10.67±0.94	09.33±0.47	10.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	21.00±2.00	11.33±1.25	15.33±0.94	17.33±0.94	40	40	38	38	-	-	-	0.00±0.00

(GE :Ethanol extract - GEE: 70% Ethanol/30% Water - GA : Acetonic extract - GAE : 70 % acetone/30%water) G : Ginger – (TE : Ethanol extract - TEE : 70% Ethanol/30% Water -TA : Acetonic extract -TAE : 70 % acetone/30%water) Tthyme. TEGE : Combination ethanol extract - TAGA : Combination acetonic extract. TAGE : Thyme acetonic extract+ Ginger ethanol extract . TEGA : Thyme ethanol extract + Ginger acetonic extract - AMC : amoxicillin - CEF : cefazolin - GEN : gentamicin - Flu : fluconazole- G: Ginger- T: Thyme. The values = the average of 3 trials ± standard deviations.

CONCLUSION

This study indicated that strains showed significant sensitivity to the extracts, especially their associations with inhibition zones diameters between 15- 40mm. The ethanolic extract of *Thymus Vulgaris* has the smallest MIC (0.145 mg/ml) which resulted in better efficacy, followed by the value of ethanolic extract of ginger which is (100mg / ml), and the greatest MIC value which is the extract of the association (122.5 mg/ml). According to our results, the antimicrobial activity was modified depending on the polarity of the solvents used. It is important to note that the effect of the combined extract of thyme and ginger TEGE shows high sensitivity (40mm) compared to those of antibiotics (\approx 25mm) towards *E. coli* ATCC11150. The tests of the antimycobacterial effect with ginger ethanolic extracts (GE), thymus (TE) and their association (TEGE) shows that the TE and TEGE extracts have an enormous antimycobacterial effect which has been confirmed by the total absence of colonies on the surface of tubes containing these extracts. These results indicate that *thymus Vulgaris* may provide suitable lead compounds for further development and possible clinical utility as a broad-spectrum antimicrobial agent.

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